

Effects of 6-week of Yoga Asana on Biochemical Variables in Adolescent Girls

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to investigate the effects of 6 week Yoga Asana training on biochemical variables in Adolescent Girls. A group of 20 adolescent girls (mean + SD: age 17.03 + 1.62 years, height 1.53 + 0.03 m, body mass 44.5 + 5.3 kg), who participated in interschool yoga competition volunteered to participate in study. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Lakshmi Bai National Institute of Physical Education, India. All participants were informed about the study aim and methodology. All the subjects agreed to the above conditions in writing. They were randomly assigned into yoga asana training (Y) and control (C) groups, n = 10 each. Yoga group (Y) was subjected to 6 week Yoga Asana training program of 30 min a day and the control group did not perform any Yoga Asana training techniques. The following biochemical parameters were determined: Haemoglobin, Uric acid, Total cholesterol, Testosterone, Triglycerides, Blood sugar, Red blood corpuscles and White blood corpuscles.

Keywords:

Yoga Asana, Biochemical Variables, Adolescent Girls

1. INTRODUCTION

In this present, fast growing world of science and technology, the human element is treated as ever before. Its goals are indistinct and unsatisfying the mechanism of modern living, the forced restriction of physical activity leading to a sedentary life, an increases amount of leisure time. Yoga exercise can help a person to develop his health along with control of various emotions like lust, love, affection, anger, greediness and provides firm control over body and mind specially to overcome most of the dangerous diseases. For this reason at present the importance of yoga is felt by the large number of person as in mast of nations.

It is now being realized in all parts of the globe that yoga is not only for better development of mind, socio-control, and spiritual, moral but also a therapy (Joshu,1995). Recent research trends have shown that it can serve as an applied science in a number of fields such as education, physical education and sports. Yogic practices are generally looked upon as exercise and many time interpreted in the light of exercise physiology the physiology of yogic practices differs from that of exercise physiology. This needs basic understanding of the concept of yoga and its relation with the technique. The nature of every yogic practices is psycho physiological and if this conceptual background is not clearly understood, the whole outlook on yogic practice will be distributed the relation of yogic exercise in terms of anatomy and physiology would remove many misconception about them (Gore, 1984). Yoga exercise are scientific means for strengthen of all living or atrophying muscle fibers and tissues. It develops the will power long with bodily strength. This aspect of yoga is technically known as a Asana which was developed

by the Latin hatha yogic into a well-organized system of physical culture (Yogendra, 1971). Yoga is also a method of self-realization which begins with the perfection of one's physical self and aspires to achieve a state of self-consciousness (Joshi, 1967). Pranayama is a science of Respiration. It consists of three phases Purak, Khumbhak, Rechak. Pranayama improve the circulation of blood and capable of producing very high pressures in the lungs and in the thorax.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A group of 20 adolescent girls (mean $\pm$ SD: age 17.03 ± 1.62 years, height 1.53 ± 0.03 m, body mass 44.5 ± 5.3 kg), who participated in interschool yoga competition volunteered to participate in study. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Lakshmbai National Institute of Physical Education, India. All participants were informed about the study aim and methodology. All the subjects agreed to the above conditions in writing. They were randomly assigned into yoga asana training (Y) and control (C) groups, $n= 10$ each. Yoga group (Y) was subjected to 6 week Yoga Asana training program of 30 min a day and the control group did not perform any Yoga Asana training techniques.

3. MEASUREMENT OF BIOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS

To measure the biochemical parameters of the adolescent girls, 5 ml of venous blood was drawn from an antecubital vein after a 12 h fast and 24 h after the last session of exercise. Haemoglobin, Uric acid, Total cholesterol, Testosterone, Triglycerides, Blood sugar, Red blood corpuscles and White blood corpuscles were determined by enzymatic method using Boehringer Mannheim kit (Mukharjee, 1997).

4. YOGASANAS 6-WEEK TRAINING PROGRAMME

The aim of asanas is to strengthen the body, clearing the impurities of nadis and to make the body fit for sitting comfortably in meditation for long hours. The present study had been undertaken to examine the effect of 6-week of Yoga Asana on Biochemical Variables in Adolescent Girls. The experimental group received training in physical postures (asanas, 30 minutes).

The asanas which were practiced every day included:

1. Matyasana (Fish pose)
2. Hal asana (Plough pose)
3. Noukasana (Boat pose)
4. Ardchakrasana and
5. Bhujangasana (Cobra poses)

Figure 1

6. RESULTS

To determine whether experimental treatment was effective in bringing about a significant change in count of biochemical variables or not, 't' test was used and analysis of data pertaining to this study are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Variables	Yoga Group			Control Group		
	Pre	Post	't' Value	Pre	Post	't' Value
Haemoglobin Hb (g.dl ⁻¹)	14.36	14.74	0.045	14.61	14.77	.002
Uric acid (mg.dl ⁻¹)	3.73	3.94	1.10	3.73	3.80	.80
Total Cholesterol (mg.dl ⁻¹)	86.3	92.1	2.47*	89.6	90.1	1.16
Testosterone	21.03	25.15	2.76*	22.03	24.16	1.27
Triglycerides	12.6	13.2	3.17*	11.4	11.9	1.75
Blood Sugar	83.6	92.45	2.56*	84.5	90.89	1.85
Red Blood Carpuscles	5.28	5.48	.0004	5.22	5.37	.071
White Blood Carpuscles	7460	7420	0.494	7530	7540	.811

*'t' value to be significant at (9) degree of freedom is 2.262.

The results of biochemical parameters in 6-week yoga asana (Y) and control (C) groups are presented in Tables 1. Significant between-group differences were found in total cholesterol ($t = 2.47^*$), testosterone ($t = 2.76^*$), triglycerides ($t = 3.17$) and blood sugar ($t = 2.56^*$) since the calculated value of t is greater than tabulated value of t (2.262) for the selected degree of freedom and level of significance whereas no significant between-group differences were noted in haemoglobin ($t = 0.045$), uric acid ($t = 1.10$), red blood corpuscles ($t = .0004$) and white blood corpuscles ($t = 0.494$) since the calculated value of t is smaller than tabulated value of t (2.262) for the selected degree of freedom and level of significance. No significant changes were noted in the control group. The graphical representation of t-value of biomechanical parameters in the yoga training (Y) and control (C) groups ($n = 10$ each) of 6 week Yoga Asana training exhibited in Fig. 1, respectively.

Figure 2

7. DISCUSSION

Physiological responses to physical training, including yoga have been studied by many investigators. It may be expected to positively influence many biochemical functions. In a previous study of Yoga, a method of learning that aims to attain the unity of mind, body, and spirit through exercise, breathing and meditation [Garfinkel, Hadi and Murugesan], that employs means like rope *mallakhamb* training, may be expected to positively influence many physiological functions including respiration. The results of this study showed that yoga training lasting 6 weeks significantly between-group differences were found in Total cholesterol ($t = 2.47^*$), testosterone ($t = 2.76^*$), Triglycerides ($t = 3.17$) and blood sugar ($t = 2.56^*$) since the calculated value of t is greater than tabulated value of t (2.262) for the selected degree of freedom and level of significance whereas no significant between-group differences were noted in Haemoglobin ($t=0.045$), Uric acid ($t=1.10$), red blood corpuscles ($t = .0004$) and white blood corpuscles ($t = 0.494$) since the calculated value of t is smaller than tabulated value of t (2.262) for the selected degree of freedom and level of significance. No significant changes were noted in the control group.

8. INFERENCE

Since calculated " t " is greater than tab $t_{.05}$, H_0 (null hypothesis) may be rejected at .05 level of significance. Thus it may be concluded that 6-week of Yogic practice training programme have a significant effect on total cholesterol ($t= 2.47^*$), testosterone ($t=2.76^*$), triglycerides ($t=3.17$) and blood sugar ($t=2.56^*$). As per the study the above remark can be given at 95% confidence.

9. CONCLUSION

Findings of this exploratory study suggest that the treatment of 6-week of yogic practices training programme showed significant improvement in total cholesterol, testosterone, triglycerides and blood sugar and not produce improvement in haemoglobin, uric acid, red blood corpuscles and white blood corpuscles.

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